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“ENHANCING LINGUISTIC AND INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCES OF PRE-SERVICE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS THROUGH MOOC”

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Annotation. *The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies is reshaping educational landscapes, offering new opportunities for the professional development of future educators. This study explores the integration of AI tools especially MOOCs into the learning process of future foreign language teachers, aiming to enhance their professional competence in pedagogical, linguistic, and digital domains. The integration of technology in education has transformed teacher training paradigms, particularly through the rise of MOOCs. These platforms offer open-access, flexible, and scalable learning opportunities that align with the demands of 21st-century education. For future foreign language teachers, MOOCs present a dynamic environment to develop both linguistic proficiency and pedagogical expertise.*

The research investigates how MOOC methodological capabilities — such as intelligent tutoring systems, automated feedback platforms, and adaptive learning technologies—support the development of key teaching skills, including lesson planning, error analysis, and learner differentiation. The findings suggest that integration of MOOC is not only fosters personalized learning and self-reflection but also promotes active engagement and autonomous learning strategies among teacher trainees. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of digital literacy and ethical awareness in the effective use of MOOC in teacher education.

Key words: *foreign language education, MOOC, technologies, professional competence of future foreign language teachers, learning strategies, digital tools in language learning, development, methodology,*

Article

Modern society has entered a new phase of its evolutionary development - the phase of digitalization of society, which is characterized by the intensive penetration of new information technologies into all spheres of human activity. The role of information technologies, including mass open online courses (here in after referred to as MOOCs), is becoming more important. At the moment, the relevance of using MOOC is one of the most discussed in the educational process, in the development of which the leading educational institutions of the world participate.

Today, the strategy of development of modern Kazakhstan is aimed at digitalization of education and society of the country. The main strategic document of this process was the "Concept of the Development of Higher Education and Science in 2023-2029", aimed at the transformation of the system of higher education and science with an emphasis on key elements, such as higher and postgraduate education in accessibility; provision of advanced personnel; development infrastructure of higher education and digital architecture; internationalization of postgraduate education; development of continuous education; improvement of citizens' digital competences". The concept integrates 3 main activities, among which there is "Technological development due to digitization, science and innovation", which aims to "Implementation of the digital university model: Implementation of the digital university model, educational programs in online format, digital educational technologies" [1].

This concept emphasizes the importance of introducing information resources into the education system for the preparation of high-quality Kazakh specialists adapted to global competition in the field of knowledge. The solution to achieving such goals is the training of a specialist who is able to quickly master new knowledge, who is able to learn throughout his life, and the use of MOOCs during training in an educational organization of higher education and in further professional

activities. According to our scientific opinion, pedagogically weighted implementation of MOOCs in the educational process will facilitate the familiarization of students with the possibilities of using MOOCs, expand their understanding of the availability of studying professional disciplines, and will form self-education and self-development skills.

MOOCs facilitate a shift from passive teacher-centered instruction to active, collaborative learning experiences. Unlike traditional language teaching, which often focuses on rote learning and decontextualized grammar exercises, MOOCs capabilities emphasizes real-world application through collaborative and task-based learning. For example, virtual discussion forums, shared document editing platforms, and interactive group projects simulate workplace communication, fostering both linguistic competence and the interpersonal skills necessary for global professional settings [2].

As for methodological capabilities of MOOCs we can enumerate the personalization and autonomy, exposure to authentic materials and multimodal content, development of pedagogical competence, collaborative and interactive learning, digital literacy and technological integration, assessment and feedback mechanisms. All of these methodological capabilities of MOOCs allow learners to enhance their professional competences as future experts. If we say about linguistic competence MOOCs contribute to continuous exposure of authentic material, for methodological skills it helps to develop new learning approaches, as for technological skills it helps to train different digital abilities for learning and teaching. Also, contribution of MOOC reflected on cultural awareness of learner by interaction with international learners and diverse perspectives on language and culture.

Literature Review. A systematic review of existing literature was conducted to establish a theoretical foundation for the study. The literature suggests that MOOCs have strong methodological capabilities to enhance the professional competence of future foreign language teachers, particularly in developing digital, linguistic, and pedagogical skills. However, the quality, contextual relevance, and integration with formal education systems are critical factors in determining their success. The use of MOOCs in teacher education has gained significant scholarly attention in recent years, particularly for their potential to enhance the professional competence of future foreign language teachers. This literature review explores key studies and theoretical perspectives that underpin the integration of MOOCs into foreign language teacher education, highlighting their methodological contributions and limitations.

Research Aim. To investigate how participation in Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) can enhance the linguistic and intercultural competence of pre-service foreign language teachers and to identify effective methodological strategies for integrating MOOCs into teacher education programs.

RQ1: How does participation in MOOCs influence the linguistic competence (e.g., vocabulary, grammar, academic writing, pronunciation) of pre-service foreign language teachers?

RQ2: Which MOOC design features (e.g., discussion forums, peer collaboration, video lectures, authentic materials) contribute most to the development of intercultural competence?

Materials and methods. The research on the methodological capabilities of MOOC in improving professional competence of future foreign language teachers follow from a general aim and objectives and involve the following types of analysis:

- Survey and Questionnaires: Conduct surveys and administer questionnaires to students in Kazakhstan to gather information about their perceptions, experiences, and preferences regarding MOOC in language learning. This can provide valuable insights into the acceptance and effectiveness of methodological capabilities of MOOC in the local context.

- Experimental Studies: Design controlled experiments to compare the language learning outcomes of students who engage in traditional classroom language instruction with those who participate in MOOC activities. Measure variables such as language proficiency, motivation, and cultural awareness to assess the impact of MOOC.

- Content Analysis: Analyze the content and structure of MOOC materials and resources used in Kazakhstani universities for future foreign language teachers. Assess how these materials align

with national language curriculum standards and evaluate their effectiveness in promoting language learning.

- Comparative Studies: Compare the effectiveness of various MOOC platforms in the Kazakhstani context. Investigate which technologies are most suitable for preparation of future foreign language teachers.

By employing a combination of these research methods, it is possible to comprehensively investigate the integration of Massive Open Online Courses in Kazakhstan, shedding light on its effectiveness, challenges, and potential for enhancing language learning in this unique linguistic and cultural context. This approach ensures a comprehensive analysis of the pedagogical implications and practical applications of MOOC.

Results and discussion. The implementation of MOOC in Kazakhstani education system knuckle down notable results contributing to the enhancement of preparing future foreign language teachers in the country. This section discusses key research findings, drawing upon studies and initiatives conducted in the Kazakhstani context.

1. Enhancing Professional Competence:

Numerous studies indicates that embedding MOOC to the teaching and learning process positively influences development of professional competence of learners. By professional competence we imply digital literacy, intercultural awareness, research skills, innovation tools in teaching, reflective practice. In Kazakhstani education system research conducted has shown that students engaging in MOOC have demonstrated significant improvements in their professional competence.

2. Enhancing Linguistic Competence:

Embedding MOOC in teaching and learning process has proven effective in enhancing linguistic development of learners. In Kazakhstan, students who participate in MOOC activities have reported higher level of improvement in their language skills, including listening, speaking, reading, listening and writing. These findings align with the global trend of MOOC enhancing linguistic competence.

3. Teacher training development:

Effective implementation of MOOC hinges on adequately trained educators. Teacher training development focuses on lesson design, classroom management, assessment, and innovation in teaching. Educators who use lesson planning templates, microteaching with video recording, assessment design tools are more successful in fostering collaborative and technology-enhanced language learning environments.

Implementation of MOOC in university system give positive results in preparing future foreign language teachers. According to the survey we can name MOOC which are commonly used.

Coursera: Coursera is one of the world's largest MOOC platforms, which is partners with leading universities, companies, organizations. This platform plays a significant role in organization of education, making it accessible to learners in Kazakhstan and worldwide. For future foreign language teachers, it is a valuable platform to gain linguistic exposure, methodological knowledge, and global teaching insights. When integrated into university curricula with proper scaffolding, Coursera can significantly enhance professional competence [3].

edX: edX is a large platform for MOOCs. edX offers multiple relevant programs for developing linguistic, methodological, and professional competencies: language learning MOOCs, digital pedagogy and educational technology (courses on online teaching, instructional design, and blended learning), intercultural communication (help teachers to build global citizenship) [4].

Udemy: Udemy is a global online learning marketplace that offers on-demand video-based courses created by independent instructors. Udemy offers a rich selection of courses that can help pre-service and in-service teachers build: linguistic competence, professional competence [5].

BBC Learning English: BBC Learning English is a free online platform created by the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) to help learners worldwide improve their English. It offers videos, audio programs, articles, and interactive activities designed for different proficiency levels — from

beginner (A1) to advanced (C1+). BBC Learning English is a flexible, authentic, and free resource that enhances linguistic, cultural, and professional competence. When integrated into teacher training programs or MOOCs, it can: provide high-quality input for developing listening and speaking skills, model authentic language use for lesson planning, foster autonomous learning habits in future teachers and their students [6].

Future Learn: FutureLearn is a UK-based MOOC platform. FutureLearn offers many courses directly supporting the professional, linguistic, and pedagogical development of pre-service teachers [7].

Despite the big amount of MOOCs, it is important to consider individual preferences and specific educational context of educators and learners. Customizing all MOOCs which suit learners' needs and objectives in Kazakhstan ensures the most effective language learning experiences.

In order to delineate the function of MOOC within the educational framework of Kazakhstan, a survey was administered to and students (22 participants) enrolled at West Kazakhstan University of Engineering and Technology, from 3rd and 4th course of bachelor degree. The following survey consist nine questions, which are related to *to* explore how MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) contribute to the development of linguistic and intercultural competences among pre-service foreign language teachers.

Questionnaire: *“Enhancing Linguistic and Intercultural Competence of Pre-Service Foreign Language Teachers Through MOOCs.”*

Dear participant,

You are invited to participate in this research study, which is part of a PhD thesis on “Enhancing Linguistic and Intercultural Competence of Pre-Service Foreign Language Teachers Through MOOCs.” The purpose of this questionnaire is to explore how MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) contribute to the development of linguistic and intercultural competences among pre-service foreign language teachers. Your responses will remain strictly confidential and will be used only for academic purposes. There are no right or wrong answers - please respond honestly based on your own experience. Thank you for your valuable contribution.

Section 1: Educational background (Tick or fill in the blanks)

1.1. Year of Study: 2nd 3rd 4th Master's

1.2. Have you had any teaching experience (including practicum, tutoring, or classroom teaching)?

1.3. How often do you participate in MOOCs?

Section 2: Self-Assessment of Linguistic Competence

(Use a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

2.1. MOOCs help me improve my English language skills (reading, writing, listening, speaking).

2.2. MOOCs provide opportunities to expand my vocabulary and grammar knowledge.

Section 3: Intercultural Competence

(Use a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

3.1. MOOCs expose me to diverse cultural perspectives and international contexts.

3.2. Participation in MOOCs improves my ability to communicate across cultures.

Section 4: Perceptions of MOOCs

(Use a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

4.1. MOOCs motivate me to take responsibility for my own learning.

4.2. MOOCs are an effective supplement to my teacher education program.

Open-ended: *What aspects of MOOCs do you find most helpful in developing linguistic and intercultural competences?*

Survey Analysis: *Enhancing Linguistic and Intercultural Competence of Pre-Service Foreign Language Teachers Through MOOCs*

Diagram 1- Section 1: Educational background

According to the Diagram 1 approximately 46,2 % of respondents are students of 4th year, 38,5 % of participants students of 3rd year and only 15,4% of participants are the students of 2nd year of study. Approximately 66,6 % of respondents had teaching experience, 33,3% didn't have any experiences Description of Experience: Among those who have experienced MOOC, development of professional, linguistic and teacher training competences are crucial. Notable outcomes include the enhancement of digital literacy and professional competence of future foreign language teachers.

MOOCs help me improve my English language skills (reading, writing, listening, speaking).

21 ответ

MOOCs provide opportunities to expand my vocabulary and grammar knowledge.

21 ответ

Diagram 2. Section 2 :Self-Assessment of Linguistic Competence

According to Diagram 2 42,9% of participants indicated that MOOCs help them to improve thier English language skills, especially speaking and listening and the same percentage of responde pointed that learners improve their vocsabulary and grammar knowledge. Description of experience: we see that using MOOCs in the classroom give to the trainers a huge opportunity to develop students' linguistic competence.

MOOCs expose me to diverse cultural perspectives and international contexts.

Participation in MOOCs improves my ability to communicate across cultures.

Diagram 3. Intercultural Competence

Diagram 3. Section 3: Intercultural competence gave us the 38,1% percentage of responds that indicated using MOOCs expose leraners to divers cultural perspective and international contexts. The same percentage of participants declared that MOOCs improve their ability to communicate across cultures. Description of experience: by using MOOCs in teaching process learners have achievements in communication with other nation people and can easily understand international context. So, with the help of MOOCs learners can easily across international bridge.

MOOCs motivate me to take responsibility for my own learning.

MOOCs are an effective supplement to my teacher education program.

Diagram 4. Section 4: Perceptions of MOOCs

47,6% percentage of responds show MOOCs as an effective supplement of thier teacher education program for participants and 42,9% of participants decided that using MOOCs motivate them to take responsability to learn. Description of experience: by using MOOCs in the classroom a huge amount of participants indicated that MOOC is the crucial instrument in pedagogical work.

Does a future foreign language teacher need to be able to fully utilize the MOOC to organize his/her educational and methodological work?

Верных ответов: 1 из 7

Diagram 5. MOOC in educational and methodological work

71,4% of respondents answer that a future foreign language teacher need to be able to fully utilize MOOC to organise his or her educational work and 42,9 % answer negatively.

In summary, the survey analysis suggests that implementation and using MOOCs in teaching process is perceived positively in Kazakhstan, with a belief in its potential to enhance professional competence of future foreign language teachers. However, challenges related to technology access and teacher training need to be addressed for more effective implementation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research results and discussions surrounding the implementation of MOOCs in Kazakhstan is developing. The survey analysis has shown its potential to improve learners attitude towards usage of MOOC, increase motivation, and develop educators digital literacy. As Kazakhstan continues to embrace the digital age, using MOOC in improving future foreign language teachers professional competence stands as a powerful tool for equipping its learners with the competitive and high-quality apparatus in a globalized world.

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